

The importance of physical education and classroom profiling in primary school

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is that physical education and profiling is so important because it provides information to each individual of which they are not aware of, and determines which goal-oriented play activity leads to the improvement of motor skills. In this paper we aim to address the issue of physical education classes in school in the current European context to better understand different perspectives that are explained by cultural, economic, social, as well as by tradition. Deeply human physical education is a particularly complex activity that systematically capitalizes on all forms of physical exercise in order to primarily increase human biological potential in accordance with social requirements. Targeted biological potential includes effects in multiple planes: optimization of physical development, demand for large functions that support physical effort, and increased ability implications of effort, improvement of motor skills, etc. At the same time, the paper includes a sociological survey based on a questionnaire, from which we wanted to learn about the perception of teachers, about different specializations, about the importance of physical education in school, about the place, schedules, factors influencing the design and benefits of physical education classes. From the analysis of specialized literature, there has been a growing awareness of the importance of school physical education classes in our country, but it should be given even more attention. Over the last three decades, sport has become much more scientific. While our advanced physiological

and technical knowledge has produced great advances and physical performances unattainable before the biggest problem, today has become passivity. Therefore, every child should understand that physical activity not only improves health, but also gives him joy, socializes but also makes him more capable in daily life. The lesson includes theoretical and practical parts. Therefore profiling is an efficient and effective way to develop the skills of advanced children in sports because every child has a tendency and finds himself in a certain sport.

Keywords: Physical Education, Motor Skills, Coordination, Balance

Introduction

The problem of low physical activity of children and adolescents has never been less so than today. This is due to many factors, but the most common is the students' lifestyle for computer games and communication on social networks. The time that parents of modern children spent on outdoor games, the current younger generation sits at the computer. At the same time, the deficit of physical activity is so great that 2-3 lessons of physical education per week may seem like a drop in the ocean, unable to affect the physical development of school students. And if we recall even the most frequent tragic cases when we exceed the standards, then the question arises: why do we need physical education in school? Maybe it is better to exclude this subject from the school curriculum at all? Such a radical approach to solving this problem cannot be considered reasonable; it is equivalent to offering guillotine as a remedy for headaches. It is necessary not to exclude physical education, but to ensure that it brings maximum benefit and becomes an integral part of the lifestyle for children. This will require a fundamental change in the teaching of this vital subject. With the onset of school life, children's significant natural physical activity is very limited. Instead of outdoor games, they should sit for a long time, first in the classroom in the stuffy classrooms, and then at home, doing homework. Active movements during breaks between classes and weekends help to compensate for the damage from an extended stay in a static position. However, modern realities are such that most children in their spare time sit still, preferring passive leisure activities. The reason for the massiveness of this phenomenon is, first of all, insufficient parental control. Unfortunately, not all parents realize how strongly the physical development of children and adolescents depends on regular physical activity. Many parents prefer to watch their child at home on the computer rather than worry about his safety, letting him go play in the yard. Not everyone has the ability and desire to take children to sports sections. Malnutrition in children,

which leads to overweight, is also a major problem. This exacerbates their delay in physical development. But parents are not the only ones to blame for their children's physical weakness. Most of the blame lies with the school. Above all, the low level of physical culture of the majority of the population is a consequence of the attitude towards teaching this subject in schools. Parents who have learned since childhood that a lesson in physical culture is something trivial, secondary and to their children they will bring a contemptuous attitude towards "physical exercise". However, the primary value for a person - his health - cannot be trivial and secondary. Few people after graduation will need knowledge of integrals or chemical formulas, but awareness of the need for regular physical activity and the use of healthy living skills will help make each person's life healthier, longer and more fruitful.

To date, teaching physical education in school has many problems, these are:

- *Outdated teaching methods;*
- *Lack of professional, conscientious specialists;*
- *Insufficient funding*

If worrying about the health of the younger generation is not an empty phrase, then the problems of teaching physical education in schools should be resolved as soon as possible. Outdated programs and methods are one of the main problems of teaching physical education in school. With a minimum set of hours for physical education lessons in school, students are required to pass standards that few can meet. Presumably, it is assumed that school students should train themselves after school hours to improve their athletic performance. But this approach is utopian, especially given the current obsession among students for computers and the internet. The task of physical education should not be to assess the physical development of children, but this development itself. The requirement to pass the standards by untrained children does not bring any benefit, it can only cause harm to health, up to tragic cases, which, unfortunately, occur more often. The solution to this problem can be an individual approach to each child, taking into account his level of physical development. Classes should not cause overload and negative emotions; only in such conditions can positive dynamics be expected from them. It is not the students who should be compared to each other, but the achievements of each child compared to their past performance.

Given the lack of time allotted in the schedule for physical education classes, it is necessary to actively develop sports in school and to include students in school sports clubs, in optional classes. Sports sections are not available to everyone, moreover, sports aimed at achieving the highest results are not always

good for health. Optional physical education in schools can make an important contribution to the physical development and health of children.

The issue of professionals

Professionalism and a responsible attitude towards their work are important for all school teachers, and especially for physical education teachers. Above all, they are entrusted with the most precious thing - the health and life of children. Being passionate about their profession and the ability to arouse students' interest in physical education are valuable, but, unfortunately, rarely seen qualities. Lack of enthusiasm and a formal attitude towards work is characteristic of many school physical education teachers. One of the main reasons for this is the low salary and lack of prestige of the teaching profession. By increasing the salary of school physical education teachers to a decent level, it would be possible to attract good specialists in this profession and increase their interest in the results of their work.

Material basis

Today, most schools do not meet modern requirements in terms of its equipment. Most schools face the following problems due to lack of funding:

- *Lack of lockers in schools for storing sportswear;*
- *Lack of showers;*
- *Obsolete gym equipment;*
- *Lack of a variety of sports equipment*

Opportunities to introduce students to the various sports they may be interested in are often missed due to insufficient supply of sports equipment in schools. The availability of skis, skates, tennis rackets, kayaks and strength training equipment would significantly expand the circle of students who want to get involved in physical education. The same goes for their pool, which for most schools remains in the category of their dreams.

The reasons why parents seek to exclude their child from physical education at school can be various: from concern for his health to unwillingness to break the certificate with a low grade. But at the heart of each of these reasons is poor physical development and health problems that do not allow students to enjoy their classes and their success in physical education lessons. But in fact, for such students, physical activity is even more necessary and for those who have

such problems. Systematic, well-chosen physical exercises, along with proper nutrition, can do wonders. This statement is true for everyone, but especially for children, because a growing organism is more sensitive to the beneficial effects of physical education. Instead of getting the coveted help that allows you to avoid physical activity, it is better to agree with the teacher about classes in a health group or remedial gymnastics and make physical education an integral part of your child's life. If the parents show perseverance, making efforts in this direction, then in the graduation class, a student who had previously remained in physical development will receive an excellent grade deserved in the certificate. And along with it - good health and excellent physical shape, which is an extremely valuable reward. All of the above applies especially to parents of overweight children. It is understood that the desire of mothers to free their children from physical education in order to protect them from the ridicule of their classmates, but for the child this can be "harm". Regular physical activity, outdoor games in physical education classes are essential for full school students like no other. A child being overweight is a huge detriment to his health and self-esteem. And this is a big mistake of parents, which you should definitely try to correct with the help of physical education, lifestyle changes and eating habits.

In our time, society does not pay due attention to physical education classes in school. Someone thinks that in school there is nothing interesting and useful in physical education lessons and it is better for the child to do extra lessons, while someone is just lazy and he / she does not go to these lessons in principle. An even more frightening trend is the fact that the promotion of a lifestyle in which sport has been given an important and fundamental role has virtually disappeared in our country. This is why it is necessary to understand and comprehend what is the benefit of physical education classes in school. Physical education classes in schools can be held in facilities available in almost every school, in an area specially equipped for training or physical activity. In the gym and on the field, training conditions must be created in accordance with established standards. They determine how many students can attend at the same time, and what should be the height of the ceilings in the room and the standards determine the mandatory presence of ventilation and heating, the necessary lighting, the number of utility rooms and changing rooms, showers and sports equipment.

Physical education lessons in school, as a rule, consist of three parts: introductory, main and final. The introductory part, or warm-up, helps prepare the baby's body for the next stress. In the main part, children learn new things physical exercises they run, jump, jump, climb a tightrope, play outdoor games, and hold relay races. And in the last part, the school students are invited to rest so that the heartbeat and pulse return to normal, and the body has time to rest.

It has been observed that physical education classes in schools are usually

tedious for children if they are not built strictly according to the curriculum. Therefore, during such lessons, children are often offered independent physical activity. The teacher conducts such classes either in the gym or outside, with or without sports equipment. It is also very useful to perform a certain system of exercises in music; it relieves children's stress, helps to develop a sense of rhythm, coordination and attention in them. The concept of "physical education in schools" also includes sports or activities in the form of games because the child is very important to have fun at the same time but also to be educated in sports knowing the importance and value of physical activity. If the teacher sees that the children are tired and do not absorb the material well, you can give them the opportunity for a few minutes to complete simple exercises, squats and bends, this helps relieve mental stress.

Primary school education is mainly aimed at improving the overall health and physical development of students, as well as the development of independent and creative thinking of primary school students. Physical education in grades 1-3 is necessary for children, as it helps to develop endurance, helps to develop dexterity, flexibility, coordination of movements and initial skills in team games. A physical education lesson in elementary school is very important. Physical education in primary school helps children to keep their bodies in good physical condition from an early age, forms a respectful attitude towards their own health and the health of others, promotes collectivism in future citizens, willingness to help, courage, reaction and zeal.

What exactly do elementary school children do in physical education classes? Physical education lessons in primary classes are mainly devoted to sports games, various competitions and competitions. Theoretical lessons usually last 3-5 minutes at the beginning of the lesson - the teacher tell the children the topic of the current lesson. In addition to relay games and competitions, a lot of attention is paid to training exercises, running, walking, jumping, climbing and throwing, and acrobatic movements.

Physical activity protects children from chronic diseases such as heart disease, type 2 diabetes and osteoporosis. Evidence-based data are also appropriate to conclude that physical activity has beneficial effects on plasma lipid levels and lipoprotein levels, on non-traditional cardiovascular risk factors (endothelial function), and on some health components, mental (self-concept, anxiety and depression). Lack of physical activity in children is a risk factor for many health problems, such as high blood pressure, weight gain, increased body fat, bad cholesterol (LDL cholesterol) which is a risk factor for heart disease, respiratory problems (respiratory), cardiovascular disease, and bone health problems. Bone strengthening activities make bones stronger; therefore, they are especially important for children, as these activities produce a strength in the bones that

promotes bone growth and strength. Balancing and stretching activities increase physical stability and flexibility, which reduces the risk of injury. Moreover, the health benefits of physical activity extend beyond physical health; it also has a positive impact in the areas of motor skills, psychological well-being, cognitive development, social competence and emotional maturity. Children who are more physically active demonstrate more concentration, faster cognitive processing, and perform better on standardized academic tests. Physical activity gives children opportunities to have fun, be with friends and family, and improve their skills to participate in more intense physical sports or sporting events. It can also improve social skills that can result in academic results: children learn to cooperate and obey rules and thus feel more connected to school and the community.

It also provides opportunities to enjoy activity in a social environment, improves sleep quality, reduces the feeling of lack of energy, helps children meet new friends, become flexible, improves physical skills, improves physical self-esteem, enhances relaxation and enables healthy growth and development. Physical activity can reduce stress, change mood, affect wakefulness and attention and as a result improve school achievement. The ability of physical activity to “activate” and produce more positive mood has been widely reported. Exercise enables children to feel good. Studies show that frequent participation in sports after school hours in childhood and adolescence is associated with a high level of participation in physical activities even in adulthood.

Performance profiling can be an effective tool in raising individual awareness of their current ability and increasing adherence to various intervention programs (Butler et al. 1993; Jones, 1993). The flexibility of their performance profile has previously helped coaches and sports psychologists better understand their athlete’s vision for a champion performer, monitor athlete progress, discrepancies between coach and athlete, and improved performance analysis after a events (Butler et al. 1992). To work effectively together, it is important that opinion mismatch is reduced. The latest research; including Study 2015 The Canadian Olympic Study conclusively shows that the two main contributors to medal-winning sports performances at the top level of elite sports are; the quality of the teacher-student relationship and the student’s awareness. These are not physical factors, they are human factors. Being aware, by undertaking sport-specific behavior profiling, is the safest way for teachers to develop a comprehensive understanding of both themselves and each of their students. Teachers become aware by learning about their coaching style, communication style, strengths and limitations. When students complete a behavioral profile, teachers know for sure their students’ individual personalities, motivators, preferred communication style, most effective training environments, and much more.

Why does profiling make important contributions to balance and coordination?

Many parents do not always understand how balance and coordination are related to their child’s learning process. Most of these skills come naturally to many children, but, for those who are left behind, they can have a direct impact on the classroom. Children who experience problems with body awareness, balance and coordination tend to struggle with focus and attention in school. Balance is an essential tool needed for controlled positions, such as sitting in a chair, so children tend to have difficulty concentrating on academic tasks when these skills are not properly developed. These children often demonstrate more nervousness, poor attitude and lack of fact-finding while listening to the teacher. Many times, the teacher or parent finds it difficult to give instructions or instructions to the child and has to repeat himself / herself before the tasks are completed. The child has to focus so much on keeping his body calm and “quiet” while sitting at his desk that his brain does not have the “space” available to learn. In addition to mental and social health benefits, taking up sports from an early age has been shown to be associated with greater benefits in elite sports because some parameters develop at this age which is very difficult after a certain age to capture these qualities technical.

Sport is a common form of leisure physical activity which has been shown to result in many health benefits. Recent systematic reviews have found that there are many psychological and social health benefits associated especially with participating in sports for children. There is consistent evidence that those who participate in club-based and / or team-based sports participation may have better psychological and social health outcomes than those who do not engage in any type of physical activity. The social nature of sport is suggested to mediate these health outcomes, although the psychological and social health benefits of participating in sport vary between children, adolescents, and adults. For children and adolescents, social health benefits are more prominent, such as the development of social skills through opportunities for social interaction and improved self-confidence. Proper age balance and coordination allows the child to engage in sports participation with a reasonable degree of success as it helps fluid body movement for the performance of physical abilities (e.g. walking in a balance beam or playing soccer). Involvement in sports is beneficial for maintaining self-regulation for daily tasks, as well as developing a social network and achieving a sense of belonging in a community or social environment. It also helps children develop and maintain proper controlled body movement while performing the task, which, when effective, limits the energy required thus minimizing fatigue. With good balance and coordination it is less likely to

injure as the child is likely to have the right postural responses when needed (e.g. opening his arms to protect himself when falling off the bicycle). The physical attributes of balance and coordination also allow for proper posture for desk tasks and subsequent success in excellent motor tasks.

The connection that profiling brings to develop balance and coordination?

Attention and concentration: The ability to hold attention to a specific task for a long period of time as core strength is not challenged.

Body Awareness: Knowing body parts and understanding body movement in space in relation to limbs and other objects to negotiate the environment or skills of the ball and bicycle. Bilateral integration: Using both hands together with one hand leading to: e.g. holding a tennis racket with the dominant hand and the non-dominant 'auxiliary' hand holding and stabilizing only between strokes. Crossing the midline: The ability to cross the imaginary line that runs from the baby's nose to the pelvis that separates the body on the left and right sides, which also affects the dominance of the hands. Hand-eye coordination: The ability to process information received from the eyes to control, direct, and direct the hands in performing a specific task such as handwriting or catching a ball. Hand dominance: Continuous use of one (usually the same) hand to perform the task, which is necessary to allow the development of refined skills. Muscular strength: A ability of a muscle to exert force against resistance (e.g. when climbing a tree to push or pull up).

Muscular endurance: The ability of a single muscle or group of muscles to exert force repeatedly against resistance to allow sustained engagement of physical task. Self-regulation: The ability to take, maintain, and change the level of alertness appropriate to a task or situation which then allows for better attention to the task. Postural control: The ability to stabilize the trunk and neck to enable limb coordination to perform a controlled task.

Body Awareness: The information that the brain receives from muscles and joints to make us aware of body position and body movement, which in turn allows abilities to become "automatic". Sensory processing: Precise processing of sensory stimulation in the environment as well as in our body for rapid and physically appropriate responses to movement. Isolated movement: The ability to move an arm or leg while still holding the rest of the body needed for refined movements (e.g. throwing the ball by hand or swimming in freestyle).

What other problems can occur when a child has difficulty in balance and coordination? When a child has difficulty with balance and coordination, you may also see difficulty with:

Motor (muscular) planning of how to perform a physical task (e.g. they can start in the third step and not the first). 'Rigid' muscle tone: Rigid muscles make limbs look lame or overly 'tight' muscles.

Spatial awareness of how they use or position their body (e.g. so that they inadvertently invade other people's personal space without knowing it). Low endurance for physical tasks (fine and gross motor). Develop prior writing skills: slow or incredibly heavy pencil strokes involving most of the letters, numbers, and early drawing.

Pencil grip: The efficiency and manner in which the pencil is held while drawing and writing is often compromised (too loose or too tight and too heavy to press). Pencil control: The accuracy with which the child moves the pencil for drawing and writing. Left-right discrimination: Conceiving a change of direction so that the child 'knows' the difference between the left and right sides of the body. Hand dominance: Continuous use of one (usually the same) hand to perform the task, which is necessary to allow the development of refined skills. Articulation: Clarification of spoken sounds and spoken language. Taking care of you: Dressing independently, holding and using the toothbrush are just a few examples. Sensory processing: Recording, interpreting and responding accurately to sensory stimulation in the environment and in their body.

What activities can help improve balance and coordination?

Unstable surfaces: Walking on unstable surfaces (eg cushions, bags, beans or blankets on the floor) that make the trunk work hard to maintain an upright position. Unstable swings and moving games, including climbing stairs and gyms on makeshift terrain. When the oscillations move in unexpected ways, it forces the trunk muscles to work harder.

Stroller walking (child 'walking' in hands while an adult holds his feet off the floor). Swimming: Involves the body to work against water resistance, thus providing a better awareness of where the body is in space. Kneeling (without touching the floor with your hands) to hit a balloon at another person. Children's dance game: Requires the child to change movement patterns often and quickly.

Games with big jumps (i.e. without steps between the "stones") challenge a child's balance. Bicycle and scooter: Both activities require the child to constantly make postural adjustments to maintain balance.

Conclusions

Finally, education and profiling in primary school is mainly aimed at improving the overall health and physical development of students, as well as the development of independent and creative thinking of primary school students. Physical education in grades 1-3 is necessary for children, as it helps to develop endurance, helps to develop skills, flexibility, coordination of movements, initial

skills in team games but also for children who have a tendency to continue the elite sport is good opportunity to capture some skills at this age, which are then impossible to achieve. Physical education develops students' competence and confidence to participate in a range of physical activities that become a central part of their lives, both inside and outside school. A high quality Physical Education curriculum enables all students to enjoy and succeed in many types of physical activity. They develop a wide range of skills and abilities to use compositional tactics, strategies and ideas to perform successfully. When they perform, they think about what they are doing, analyze the situation, and make decisions. They also reflect on their own and others' performances and find ways to improve them. As a result, they develop the confidence to participate in various physical activities and learn about the value of a healthy and active lifestyle.

They work as individuals, in groups and in teams, developing the concepts of justice and personal and social responsibility. Through the range of experiences that physical education offers, they learn how to be effective in competitive, creative and challenging situations. This teamwork teaches the importance of working together, learning students' strengths and weaknesses and how to work within the parameters of the team concept. These important benefits help lifelong learners work with others to achieve the desired result both individually and within the group. Physical education programs can only offer these benefits if they are well planned and implemented. The U.S. Department of Health and Human Services recommends that children have at least one hour of physical activity each day, which should include strengthening muscles and bones because it is the most fundamental part of an individual's overall development. Supporting schools to establish physical education on a daily basis can provide students with the ability and confidence to be physically active throughout life. Therefore, it is very important that physical education and profiling are seen with great importance by state institutions!

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The importance of improving the education and singular-child-focused services by the support/assistant teachers for increasing the inclusiveness of the special need children, especially the children with autism, in the preschool and primary education system

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Abstract

The support/assistant teachers, who work with special needs children in preschool and primary education, play an important function in the integration and inclusion of these children in the mainstream education system. Last years the number of these support/assistant teachers has been growing, especially in the preschool institutions of Tirana. When recruiting in the service, assistant teachers some issues would be raised by the principals, administrators, psycho-social staff in the preschool institutions, education experts, etc: "Are there enough support/assistant teachers to provide support and services for all the children with disabilities? Are they trained as well as to be prepared for in-service working? How they offer they services and which are the results of their work?"

Key words: *child education, assessment, abilities*